

Stability Constants of some Bivalent Metal Complexes with 2-Hydroxy-3,5-dimethylacetophenone Oxime

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THE present communication reports the determination of stability constants of Pd^{II}, Cu^{II}, VO^{II}, UO₂^{II}, Be^{II}, Zn^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Mn^{II} and Cd^{II} complexes with 2-hydroxy-3,5-dimethylacetophenone oxime (HDMAOX) at 27 ± 0.2° in 75% (v/v) dioxane-water medium at different ionic strengths.

Experimental

The ligand (HDMAOX) was prepared as reported earlier¹.

The following sets of solutions were titrated against standard carbonate-free sodium hydroxide solution (0.05 M): (i) 0.05 M HClO₄, (ii) (i) + 0.01 M HDMAOX and (iii) (ii) + 0.008 M metal ion.

The apparent volume of 75% dioxane + 25% water mixture (v/v) was multiplied by appropriate correction factor² to obtain the real volume. Ionic strengths of 0.1, 0.05 and 0.01 M were maintained by adding required amount of NaClO₄. The pH measurements were made on a Systronic 335 digital pH-meter and corrected by using Van Uitert and Hass equation³. Proton-ligand and metal-ligand stability constants (Table 1) were calculated by the method of Irving and Rossotti⁴.

TABLE 1—PROTON-LIGAND AND METAL-LIGAND CONSTANTS WITH HDMAOX AT 27 ± 0.2° IN 75% DIOXANE MEDIUM AT DIFFERENT IONIC STRENGTHS

Cation	$\mu = 0.1 M$		$\mu = 0.05 M$		$\mu = 0.01 M$	
	log K ₁	log K ₂	log K ₁	log K ₂	log K ₁	log K ₂
(H ⁺)	10.80	—	10.90	—	11.15	—
Pd ^{II}	11.45	10.20	11.51	10.35	11.72	10.61
Cu ^{II}	11.00	9.75	11.15	9.85	11.40	10.00
VO ^{II}	10.50	9.67	10.63	9.71	10.83	9.81
UO ₂ ^{II}	10.05	9.40	10.20	9.47	10.48	9.59
Be ^{II}	8.70	7.72	8.88	7.80	9.15	7.91
Zn ^{II}	8.30	6.75	8.46	6.87	8.70	7.05
Ni ^{II}	8.02	5.35	8.25	5.50	8.65	5.71
Co ^{II}	7.25	5.80	7.38	5.91	7.58	6.09
Mn ^{II}	6.17	5.70	6.37	5.81	6.72	6.00
Cd ^{II}	5.20	4.17	5.38	4.23	5.72	4.35

Results and Discussions

The ligand (HDMAOX) behaved as a monoprotic acid due to deprotonation of the phenolic OH group *ortho* to the oximino group from which the proton was replaced by the metal ions during complex formation. This was evident from the fact that the metal titration curves were well-separated from the ligand titration curves.

Values of $\bar{n} > 2$ were not obtained in any case which suggested that there are only two complexes, viz 1:1 and 1:2 in the systems. The order of stability constants of bivalent metal complexes was found to be: Pd^{II} > Cu^{II} > VO^{II} > UO₂^{II} > Be^{II} > Zn^{II} > Ni^{II} > Co^{II} > Mn^{II} > Cd^{II}, which is in agreement with the Irving-Williams⁵ order.

References

- U. K. JETLEY, J. SINGH and S. N. RASTOGI, *Chem. Era*, 1979, 15, 23.
- U. B. RAO and H. B. MATHUR, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1969, 7, 1234.
- L. G. VAN UITERT and C. G. HASS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 45.
- H. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3397.
- H. IRVING and R. J. P. WILLIAMS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3192.

Potentiometric Studies of Complex Formation of some Trivalent Rare Earths with *p,p'*-Bromosulphonosalicylidene Anil

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IN this communication we report the result of our potentiometric investigation of the Schiff base ligand (H₂L) *p,p'*-bromosulphonosalicylidene anil and its complexes with trivalent rare earth metal ions like Pr^{III}, Nd^{III}, Sm^{III} and Gd^{III}. The study has been carried out in aqueous medium at 25, 35 and 45° using Calvin-Bjerrum¹ pH-titration technique as adopted by Irving and Rossotti². The ionic strength (*I*) has been maintained approximately constant at 0.1 M (NaClO₄).

Experimental

Preparation of the ligand: The Schiff base ligand *p,p'*-bromosulphonosalicylidene anil was prepared as described earlier³ and purity of the compound was checked by elemental analysis.

Carbonate-free sodium hydroxide solution and double distilled water were used. Rare earth metals were estimated by EDTA method⁴. The metal perchlorates were dissolved in 0.1 M HClO₄ to avoid metal hydrolysis.

pH titration: Following sets of titrations were performed at 25 (Fig. 1), 35 and 45° against standard alkali solution (~0.4 M): (i) 10 ml 0.1 M HClO₄ + 5 ml 1 M NaClO₄ + 35 ml water, (ii) 10 ml 0.1 M HClO₄ + 5 ml 1 M NaClO₄ + 20 ml 4 × 10⁻³ M ligand + 15 ml water and (iii) 5 ml 0.1 M HClO₄ + 5 ml 1 M NaClO₄ + 5 ml 0.01 M metal ion solution + 20 ml 4 × 10⁻³ M ligand + 15 ml water.